

Zeolite Assisted Dehydration of Terpenic Alcohols : Convenient Synthesis of 1,3-Dienes and Oxepane[†]

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Terpenic alcohols undergo facile dehydration over H-ZSM-5 to yield 1,3-dienes, such as farnesenes, ocimene, myrcene and isoprene. Studies on homoallylic alcohol (1e) gave oxepane (2e).

There is an increasing demand for clean and efficient organic synthesis, and selectivity and recycling are the keys to achieve this. The last decade has witnessed considerable resurgence of interest in the area of zeolite induced organic transformations. Recently, the excellent reviews on the utility of zeolites in organic synthesis have appeared^{1,2}.

The conjugated dienes are versatile building block in the synthesis of organic natural products especially as a component of the Diels-Alder reaction. Moreover, a wide variety of biological activities are associated with conjugated dienes, the prominent among them are insect sex pheromone³ and organoleptic properties⁴. In recent years a large number of methods for the synthesis of conjugated dienes have appeared. Among others, the methods utilising organometallic reagents, modified Wittig reagents, thermal ring opening of cyclobutenes and sulfolenes⁵ have received considerable interest.

Alternatively, the dehydration of allyl alcohols with a variety of reagents has been the subject of numerous studies. Earlier workers have examined the dehydration of terpenic-allyl alcohols such as farnesol, nerolidol, geraneol, linalool etc. with a variety of acidic, basic as well as metallic reagents^{6–8}. In one of these studies a mixture of acyclic and monocyclic sesquiterpenes were reported on dehydration of farnesol and nerolidol with KHSO_4 at 170°, on the other hand base-catalyzed dehydration of farnesol at 210° gave sesquiterpenes and other hydrocarbons⁶. Other reagents used for such dehydration include POCl_3 /pyridine or DMSO at 160°⁷. The conversion of allyl alcohols to the corresponding dienes was also achieved through monoepoxidation, conversion to 3-ene-1,2-diol and subsequent treatment with PBr_3 .CuBr⁸. Synthesis of isoprene was achieved from 2-methylbutanal by treatment with boron zeolites at 400° in 51% yield⁹. Recently, the development of synthetic routes for six- to nine-membered oxygen heterocycles has received considerable attention due to the interesting biological activity of these compounds¹⁰.

TABLE 1—DEHYDRATION OF VARIOUS ALCOHOLS OVER H-ZSM-5ⁱ.

Entry no.	Alcohol	Products		Reaction time	Yield
		Diene	Rearranged product		
1 ⁱⁱ					8h/80%
2 ⁱⁱ					7h/41%
3					2h/98.7%
4					10h/98%
5 ⁱⁱⁱ					10h/79%

ⁱ All the reactions were carried out in the presence of H-ZSM-5 in refluxing benzene except entry-4 which was carried out in a sealed glass tube at 90°.

ⁱⁱ Products were characterized by ir, nmr, uv and GC-MS, in agreement with reported data.

ⁱⁱⁱ No dehydrated product, nonseparable mixture of two diastereomers (1 : 2).

Results and Discussion

As a part of our continuing efforts to explore the novel utilities of zeolite mediated reactions¹¹, we report herein dehydration of various terpenic allyl alcohols over H-ZSM-5 to get 1,3-dienes. A mixture of allyl alcohol (1a–e), H-

[†]Dedicated to Dr. Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

ZSM-5 and benzene was heated at the temperature and for the period mentioned in Table 1. Subsequent filtration, removal of solvent and chromatographic separation yielded the dienes (**2a-d** and oxepane **2e** respectively) accompanied by minor amount of rearranged alcohol (**3a,b**) (Scheme 1). The acid form of zeolite Na-ZSM-5 (Si/Al = 65) was ob-

Scheme 1

tained through successive ion-exchange with 1 M NH_4NO_3 solution (3 times) and subsequent heating at 673 K for 6 h. Alcohols **1c** and **1e** were obtained through NaBH_4 reduction in the presence of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of β -ionone¹² and Grignard reaction of melonal with allyl magnesium bromide respectively.

Interestingly treatment of β -dimethylallyl alcohol (prenol **1d**, entry-4) with H-ZSM-5 gave only dehydrated product, namely, isoprene and no allylic rearrangement was observed in this reaction. Studies on homoallylic alcohol (**1e**, entry-5) gave cyclized oxepane **2e** in 79% yield. Absence of band at 3400 cm^{-1} in ir spectrum and presence of molecular ion peak at m/z 182 in mass spectrum indicated the formation of compound **2e**. ^{13}C nmr spectrum of compound **2e** showed signals at δ 138 and 115 for olefinic carbons and at δ 76 and 74 for etherial carbons. Primary alcohols such as melonal and citronellol did not undergo dehydration or cyclization reaction.

In conclusion, the present procedure provides mild and facile route for the synthesis of conjugated dienes and oxepane.

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on Nicolet Impact-400 FT IR spectrometer, 300 MHz ^1H nmr and 75 MHz ^{13}C nmr spectra on a Varian XL-300 spectrometer, 60 MHz ^1H nmr spectra on a Hitachi R-600 FT-NMR spectrometer and mass spectra on a GC-MS Hewlett-Packard instrument at 70 eV.

General procedure for dehydration of alcohols (1a-c, e) over H-ZSM-5: A mixture of alcohol **1a-c, e** (3.5 mmol), H-ZSM-5 (300 mg) and dry benzene (6 ml) was heated for a period mentioned in Table 1. Progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc or glc. Catalyst was filtered and washed with ethyl acetate (3×10 ml). Combined filtrates was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield a residue which was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel.

The products were characterized by ir, nmr and GC-MS spectral properties.

Dehydration of β -dimethylallyl alcohol (1d) over H-ZSM-5: A mixture of prenol **1d** (774 mg, 9 mmol), H-ZSM-5 (300 mg) and dry benzene (1.5 ml) was heated at 90° in a sealed glass tube, reaction mixture was cooled to 0° and analyzed by gas chromatography. The formation of isoprene was detected by comparison with the authentic sample.

Diastereomers of compound 2e: ν_{max} (neat) 3076, 2973, 2933, 1642, 1459, 1328, 1284, 1142 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) 5.85 (1H, m), 5.05 (1H, m), 4.8 (1H, m), 3.76 (1H, ddd, J 0.73, 5.67, 8.24 Hz), 3.18 (1H, dt, J 3.29, 8.97 Hz), 1.15 (3H, s), 1.12 (3H, s), 1.4–2.4 (9H, m), 0.9 (3H, d, J 6.95 Hz), 0.81 (3H, d, J 6.77 Hz); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) 138.98, 138.92, 115.82, 115.67, 76.07, 74.39, 73.65, 41.64, 41.02, 40.37, 40.03, 39.7, 39.48, 37.62, 35.54, 29.09, 28.75, 27.81, 27.47, 22.14, 19.02, 18.61, 12.07; m/z 182 (M^+).

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